

The Effects of Texture and Microstructure on the Thermal Cycling Creep of Ti-6Al-4V with and without Fibre Reinforcement

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ABSTRACT

Pole figures have been obtained for the α phase of Ti-6Al-4V in the form of (i) plate, hot rolled down to a thickness of about 1 mm, (ii) hot pack rolled thin foils, (iii) a stack of such foils hot isostatically pressed to a sheet about 1 mm thick, and (iv) composite material made by stacking alternate layers of foil and arrays of SiC monofilament. All of these materials exhibited considerable anisotropy between through-thickness and in-plane directions, with a general tendency for basal planes to lie in the plane of the sheet. In addition, the as-rolled materials showed in-plane anisotropy, with basal planes tilted towards the rolling direction. Creep strain histories have been measured for the rolled unreinforced material, loaded parallel or normal to the rolling direction, and for the composite, loaded transverse to the fibre direction. Average strain rates have been compared with those of specimens held isothermally at the corresponding "diffusional mean" temperature. The creep rate of the composite was considerably enhanced by thermal cycling, as a consequence of the continual regeneration of internal stresses from differential thermal expansion. Specimens were observed to creep in the reverse sense to the applied load during part of the cycle. The main features of the observed creep strain history are in agreement with the predictions of a numerical model based on volume-averaged matrix stresses. The unreinforced rolled material showed different average creep rates when loaded in the two directions and also exhibited periods of negative creep in both cases. This behaviour is attributed largely to microstructural anisotropy and changes in the proportion of the two phases during cycling, causing effects qualitatively similar to those occurring in the composites.

Keywords: texture, creep, thermal cycling, MMCs, titanium, long fibre reinforcement, internal stresses

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of texture during thermomechanical treatments, and its effects on subsequent mechanical behaviour, has been extensively studied¹⁻⁹ for α -titanium and the α/β alloy Ti-6Al-4V. The high temperature behaviour of the Ti-6Al-4V alloy is of particular interest since it can be superplastically deformed. Texture is expected to have a strong influence on the deformation characteristics of material based on the hcp α -Ti structure, since none of the slip systems which are normally active at ambient temperatures allow dislocation glide in any directions inclined to the basal plane¹⁰. Relatively strong textures are readily developed during deformation processing of titanium. For example, in rolled sheet, plate and foil there is commonly a tendency for basal planes to lie within the plane of the sheet. Depending on the conditions, however, the basal plane normals may also tend to be tilted towards the rolling direction or the transverse direction. The

observed texture is also dependent on the cooling conditions after deformation². In addition to the anisotropy of yield stress, α -Ti shows appreciable orientation dependence for its Young's modulus (which falls from about 142 GPa parallel to the c-axis to about 105 GPa within the basal plane⁵) and thermal expansivity (average values up to 700°C $\sim 13.4 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ parallel to the c-axis, compared with $\sim 11.0 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ along the a-axis¹¹).

However, analysis of texture development is complicated by the fact that processing often takes place with a different proportion of β (bcc) phase than is present at room temperature. Pure titanium changes from fully α to fully β on heating above 1155 K. The Ti-6Al-4V alloy, on the other hand, has about 10vol% of β at room temperature, rising to 20% at 500 K, 40% at 1000 K and 100% at 1300 K. In general, the β phase is softer and deforms more readily than the α phase. At elevated temperatures, at least for low applied stresses and strain rates (i.e. under superplastic conditions), the alloy is reported^{8,9} to deform predominantly by grain boundary sliding of β grains, with the original α grains remaining essentially undeformed. Changes are, however, generated during this process in the α -phase texture as measured at room temperature, since a substantial amount of (deformed) β transforms to α during cooling. In interpreting the observed deformation behaviour of the alloy at room temperature, attention is commonly drawn^{2,5-9,12} to the importance of microstructural anisotropy. It seems likely that the observed anisotropy of plastic strain for Ti-6Al-4V specimens deformed at room temperature is not due to texture of the α -phase, but rather to alignment of the microstructure.

In general, metal matrix composites have been found to exhibit texture development characteristics which are similar to those of the parent alloy. It is, however, commonly found that the strengths of the textures developed are considerably weaker in the composites¹³⁻¹⁵. Little attention has been paid to the influence of matrix texture on the behaviour of MMCs, at least with fibre composites. This is not surprising, since the microstructural anisotropy caused by the fibres would be expected to dominate any effects of texture.

Creep of discontinuously-reinforced MMCs is substantially modified by the imposition of thermal cycling¹⁶⁻²⁰, which continuously regenerates internal thermal stresses. Asymmetric relaxation of these stresses during the cycle often causes pronounced enhancement of the average creep rate. Several models²⁰⁻²⁴ have been developed for creep of MMCs by invoking similar creep rate equations to those applicable to the unreinforced matrix, but using some appropriate volume-averaged matrix (deviatoric) stress within the composite (for example, as calculated with the mean field version of the Eshelby method²⁵⁻²⁸) in place of the applied stress. A central problem concerns the continuing effect of stress relaxation processes on the thermal stress field in the matrix. This is particularly important for thermal cycling creep, since relaxation of thermal stresses is dynamic and does not decay in significance as the test continues.

Thermal cycling effects have also been studied²⁹⁻³³ in long fibre MMCs, primarily under axial loading. In general, thermal cycling is found to have little effect on the behaviour when loaded along the fibre direction, but does cause enhancement of creep under transverse loading^{34,35}. This is consistent with a progressive transfer of load to the fibres under axial loading, but matrix creep continuing in a quasi steady state for the transverse case.

In fact, enhancement of creep on thermal cycling was first observed³⁶⁻³⁸ for unreinforced polycrystalline (non-cubic) metals such as zinc and uranium, which have anisotropic thermal expansivities. A change in temperature leads to internal stresses in these materials in a similar way to that which occurs in composites. Pronounced effects might be expected when strong crystallographic textures are present. This suggests that attention should be paid to texture when examining MMCs based on non-cubic metals, especially if the composite and the unreinforced material have different textures.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1. Material Production

The supplied material had been produced by two different routes. Firstly, Ti-6Al-4V plate was hot rolled down to sheet with a thickness of about 1 mm, then annealed at 785°C for 15 minutes

followed by air cooling. Secondly, similar plate was hot pack rolled in the fully β temperature range down to a thickness of 200 μm , followed by chemical milling to 100 μm . These foils were then further processed by hot isostatic pressing (at 900°C, with 70-90 MPa of pressure, for around 30 minutes) to make sheets about 1 mm thick, with or without arrays of aligned SiC monofilaments interleaved between the foils to give a fibre volume fraction of about 35%. In both cases, the foils were stacked with no specific alignment, so that individual rolling directions were either parallel or normal to those of the other foils in the stack. The fibres used were W-cored, stoichiometric "Sigma" SiC CVD monofilaments (100 μm diameter) with a surface coating of duplex TiB₂/C (1 μm of each). Tensile specimens were prepared by electrical discharge machining. Flanges at the top and bottom of the gauge length are incorporated in the specimen shape to interrupt the scanning laser beam and allow length changes to be monitored (see §2.3).

2.2 Texture and Microstructure

Texture measurements were made with a Philips PW1078 goniometer, using Cu K α radiation and a slit width of 0.75 mm. Pole figures were obtained for (0002) and {1 $\bar{1}$ 0} planes, but only those for (0002) are shown here. Measurements were made at tilt angles up to 75°. Specimens were also examined using optical microscopy. Kroll's reagent was used to reveal the grain structure.

2.3 Mechanical Testing

Creep testing was carried out on three of the materials. These were the hot rolled sheet, loaded (a) along the rolling direction and (b) along the transverse direction, and (c) the composite loaded transverse to the fibre axis. In all three cases, the test was carried out (i) with a specific thermal history during the cycle (see Figure 1) and (ii) isothermally at the "diffusional mean" temperature (average temperature of the cycle, weighted for the temperature dependence of the diffusion coefficient^{16,20}), which in this case was 909 K. Strain monitoring during creep was carried out using scanning laser extensometry. Full details are given elsewhere³⁹. Resolution is about $\pm 1 \mu\text{m}$. Specimen heating was by an elliptical dipole radiant furnace. Cooling was achieved by passing high purity argon up the quartz tube surrounding the specimen. The thermal cycle was monitored by a programmable controller, governed by a thermocouple spot welded to the specimen. A static tensile load was applied by adding weights to the scale pan.

The thermal expansivity of the unreinforced titanium was measured by dilatometry. It was found that the experimental dependence of expansivity on temperature was represented very well by the linear expression

$$\alpha = 7.171 \cdot 10^{-6} + 5.57 \cdot 10^{-9} T \quad (1)$$

The thermal expansivity values for composite specimens were calculated using the Eshelby method from constituent expansivities, fibre volume fraction and aspect ratio. The expansivity of the SiC fibre was taken as isotropic, with a constant value of $4.0 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$. Creep strain histories were obtained from the extensometry data by subtracting the elastic thermal expansion expected for the composite.

2.4 Modelling of Creep

A numerical model has been set up to predict the changing stress field within the composite during testing, and hence the creep strain history. This is based on evaluating the volume-averaged matrix stresses at any point during the process, using the Eshelby method²⁰, from the applied load, current temperature and the temperature at which the composite would be free of thermal stress - the effective stress-free temperature, T_{esf} . The instantaneous strain rate is then calculated from the deviatoric stresses in the two principal planes containing the loading direction. A Dorn-type power law creep expression⁴⁰ relating strain rate to deviatoric stress was employed

$$\dot{\epsilon} = A \left(\frac{\Delta\sigma}{G} \right)^{4.3} \frac{G b D_0}{k T} \exp\left(\frac{-Q_v}{R T} \right) \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta\sigma$ is the deviatoric stress, G is the matrix shear modulus, b is the Burgers vector, D_0 is the pre-exponential constant, Q_v the activation energy for volume self-diffusion, k is the Boltzmann constant, R is the gas constant and A is the Dorn constant. The values of D_0 and Q_v used in the current work were $1.0 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, 247 kJ mol^{-1} respectively. In order to obtain the predictions shown below, the Dorn constant, A , was taken to have a value of 1000 for the composite and 500 for the unreinforced matrix.

Stress relaxation is simulated by allowing a variation during the cycle of T_{esf} . The value of T_{esf} may be regarded as characterising the relaxation state of the composite. There will in general be a tendency for T_{esf} to alter so as to become closer to the current actual temperature. This change will take place more quickly at higher temperatures. Also, the degree to which the value of T_{esf} manages to follow the actual temperature will be greater when the cooling and heating rates are slow. For many cycle times of practical interest, it is expected that T_{esf} will lag behind the actual temperature and only approach it at high temperatures. The variation of T_{esf} with time during the cycle which was assumed for the predictions in the current paper is shown in Figure 1, together with the actual thermal history imposed. Fuller details are given elsewhere³⁵.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Microstructure

Pole figures, in simplified form, are shown in Figure 2 for the four materials studied. All of the specimens are textured, showing a preference for the basal planes to lie parallel to the plane of the sheet. For the hot-rolled sheet and the hot-pack rolled foils, (a) and (b), there is also a tendency for the basal planes to be tilted towards the rolling direction. For the HIPed stack of foils, (c), the two in-plane directions were indistinguishable and, as expected, no in-plane anisotropy is exhibited. For the composite, (d), the peak in orientation probability for the basal plane normals is also in the through-thickness direction, but there is now a slight tendency for misorientation by tilting of these normals towards the direction transverse to the fibre axis. This is consistent with the pattern for the unreinforced stack, when account is taken of a tendency for the foils to be rotated in this direction as they consolidate around the fibres.

Optical micrographs, shown in Figure 3, illustrate the grain structure and distribution of the β phase in these materials. The grain structures are in all cases relatively fine and equiaxed. An example is shown in Figure 3(a), which shows a specimen etched to reveal the α grain boundaries. In the hot rolled sheet, the β phase is distributed as stringers aligned along the rolling direction, as can be inferred from the two sections shown, (c) and (d). The as-rolled foils showed similar structures. For the HIPed stack, alignment parallel to the individual foil rolling directions could be detected, although it was weaker than in the as-rolled material. Because of the random stacking, there was no overall alignment. In the composite, (b), the β phase distribution is fairly isotropic, although a hint of in-plane layering persists.

3.2 Creep Behaviour

A comparison is shown in Figure 4 between measured and modelled creep strain histories for the composite, during isothermal and thermally cycled loading. The isothermal creep rate at \bar{T} is much less than the average rate during cycling, for both modelled and measured data. It can also be seen that the model predicts two regions of reverse creep which are in fair correspondence with the observed behaviour. This reverse creep arises because the thermal stresses can result in the matrix being under compression, with respect to at least one of the other principal directions, even when account is taken of the stresses from the applied tensile load.

Data are shown in Figure 5 for the hot rolled unreinforced material. In this case experimental plots are shown for loading parallel to either the rolling or the transverse directions. The large difference between the average creep rates during isothermal and thermally cycled loading is now absent. However, there is evidence of some anisotropy within the specimen, since the average creep rates differ for the two orientations under both isothermal and, particularly, thermally cycled conditions. Moreover, a small degree of reverse creep is exhibited within the cycle for

both orientations. Neither of these effects is predicted by the model, since the material is assumed isotropic and should therefore be free of thermal stresses.

Although the explanation of this behaviour is not entirely clear, some suggestive points can be identified. For example, it seems unlikely that crystallographic texture of the α phase is playing the dominant role. While the measured texture might be strong enough to generate reverse creep, the recorded in-plane anisotropy is weak and unlikely to cause the observed difference between the creep rates in the two directions. The most likely origin of this difference is the anisotropy of β phase distribution. It is probable that much of the deformation is concentrated in the β phase. Also, it should be remembered that the proportion of β in the microstructure is varying between about 20% and 40% during the thermal cycle. Changes in deformation mechanism could occur over the cycle, possibly allowing sliding at β - β grain boundaries at high temperatures. Such effects might contribute to the observation of greater differences between the two cases when thermally cycled than when loaded isothermally. Evidently more experimental evidence is required. For example, measurement of changes in texture induced by the loading would be of interest. It may nevertheless be noted here that predicted and observed creep histories are in broad agreement, indicating that the matrix creep characteristics are fairly well represented by the strain rate parameters used. Neither texture nor microstructural anisotropy in the matrix seem likely to affect the behaviour of the composite significantly

4. CONCLUSIONS

- (a) A provisional study has been made of the matrix α phase texture and α/β microstructure of Ti-6Al-4V, with and without fibre reinforcement. In all cases, there was a tendency for basal planes to lie parallel to the plane of the sheet. In-plane anisotropy of texture was also detected for rolled sheet and foil, but this was relatively weak. There was, however, a tendency for alignment of β grains along the rolling direction.
- (b) The creep behaviour of long fibre MMCs during thermal cycling under an applied transverse load has been modelled using volume-averaged matrix stresses. Creep rates have then been predicted from a power law equation. To represent stress relaxation during the cycle, a variation has been proposed in the effective stress-free temperature, T_{esf} , at which the matrix would be unstressed if the applied load were removed. A fairly arbitrary variation of T_{esf} during the cycle has been used in the simulations, although the form was of the general shape expected on simple theoretical grounds.
- (c) Fairly good agreement was obtained between predicted and observed creep strain histories, based on a single type of thermal cycle and a single applied load. This was the case for both unreinforced material and the composite, under transverse loading. Reverse creep, counter to the direction of loading, was both observed and predicted for the composite during parts of the thermal cycle.
- (d) The unreinforced material also exhibited a limited amount of reverse creep during the thermal cycle. This is indicative of some anisotropy within the material. The measured texture could have caused this, although deformation was probably concentrated in the β phase. Also, differences observed between loading parallel and transverse to the rolling direction are difficult to explain on this basis. It is therefore suggested that anisotropy in the distribution of the β phase at least contributed to the observed behaviour.

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Figure 1 Thermal history employed experimentally and assumed corresponding variation of T_{esf} .

Figure 2 Pole figures for (0002) planes of the α phase within Ti-6Al-4V. (a) Hot rolled sheet, (b) Hot pack rolled foil, (c) HIPed stack of foils and (d) HIPed composite. The contours are random.

Figure 3 Optical micrographs for specimens in the as-fabricated state. The sections are those containing the two directions shown in brackets (RD-rolling direction, TD-transverse direction, TT-through thickness direction, FD-fibre direction). (a) composite (FD-TD), (b) composite (FD-TT), (c) hot rolled sheet (TD-TT), (d) hot rolled sheet (RD-TT)

Figure 4 Comparison between measured and modelled creep strain data for the composite material under a transverse 20 MPa load. Data are shown for both a thermally cycled specimen and one held at the diffusional mean temperature, \bar{T} .

Figure 5 Comparison between measured and modelled creep strain data for unreinforced hot rolled Ti-6Al-4V under a 20 MPa load. Experimental data are shown for loading along the rolling direction (RD) and the transverse direction (TD). Plots are given both for thermal cycling and for isothermal heating at the diffusional mean temperature.